

BACHELOR INFORMATICA

UNIVERSITY OF AMSTERDAM

Bridging the Information Gap: Enhancing Decision Support through Learning Trajectories

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Abstract

This bachelor's thesis explores the dropout rate for the *BSc Informatica*, which is higher than the other College of Informatics (CoI) bachelor's programs. Due to the relatively high dropout rate at the start of the program, and the relatively high percentage of students that transfer within the CoI, there is an implication of an information gap. The aim is to identify this information gap and propose a method to provide customizable information.

The information gap was identified through the analysis of the data we gathered from both current students of the CoI and prospective students. One significant finding is that many students missed information about the program's content, which could have been found in the Course Catalogue. The thesis proposes a system to bridge this gap. The created system visualizes the content of the Course Catalogue, making use of the learning trajectories; almost every course in the *BSc Informatica* belongs to at least one trajectory, and the trajectories can be used to both show the relation between courses and give an idea of what the most important components are in the entire program. Students have shared that they think using trajectories would be useful, under the condition that the *meaning* of the trajectories becomes more clear; future students might not understand what they mean.

To be able to visualize the content of the program, a customization method that uses explicit user action is required. Two different interactive graphs, the Sunburst, and the Treemap, have been implemented to hierarchically present this information to students. These new visualization methods are proven to be more effective than the already existing visualization, which can be found for current students on Datanose. This research provides new insights into the field of preventing dropouts by using interactive graphs and real-world data.

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Introduction

1.1 Context

All study programs have dropouts due to many different reasons, but the bachelor's degree in *Informatica* has a relatively high dropout rate. At the University of Amsterdam, the average dropout rate for the bachelor's program *Informatica* since 2003 is 46.1 % (with a standard deviation of 11.8), while the average dropout rate for the FNWI (faculty of science) is 39.1 % (with a standard deviation of 10.2). The other bachelor's programs in the College of Informatics, *Informatiekunde* and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie*, have average dropout rates of respectively 36.4 % and 42.8 %. Figures 1.1 and 1.2 show how the average dropout rate for the bachelors that are part of the College of Informatics has changed in the past twenty years [23]. The goal of this thesis is to gain insight into this issue and be able to maximize the graduation rate and minimize the dropout rate without negatively affecting the quality of education.

Figure 1.1: Comparison between the average dropout rate of the entire faculty and the three bachelor's programs in the College of Informatics over the years. This figure is created using spline interpolation to make it more readable.

Figure 1.2: The dropout rate for the three bachelor’s programs in the College of Informatics: *Informatica* (Computer Science), *Informatiekunde* (Information Science) and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* (Artificial Intelligence). The figure shows the data from the past years and does not make use of an interpolation method to show the clear differences between the years; including the extreme values.

A high dropout rate for students in a computer science-related study is not only the case for the UvA. A lot of students leave the program in the first semester [37], which could have various reasons; for example, a student can enroll in different programs. This would mean that whenever they eventually decide to join a different program, this would count as a dropout. However, some students drop out of the program despite having chosen it.

According to a study involving dropouts from universities in Europe, the reasons to drop out of university can be divided into nine different dimensions: study conditions, academic integration, social integration, personal efforts and motivation, information and admission requirements, prior academic achievement, personal characteristics, sociodemographic background, and external conditions [31].

If students withdraw from the program in the first year or semester, it suggests that the information dimension could be one of the most important dimensions in this decision; leaving the program early seems to indicate a lack of knowledge or a knowledge gap. *Informatica* is a very interesting but complex and technical field that requires all different kinds of skills: mathematics, logic, programming, and more. Students who are not prepared for this might get overwhelmed and struggle to keep up, which might result in dropping out. *Informatica* is not the only program at the College of Informatics: *Informatiekunde* and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* are similar to *Informatica* in certain areas. Figure 1.3 shows that there is a relatively large group of dropouts that transfer to one of the other College of Informatics programs; this could be an indication of a lack of knowledge of the differences between these programs.

Figure 1.3: This figure shows which programs students follow after they drop out of the *Informatica* (CS) bachelor’s program. This data only includes the students for whom it is known which program they followed after dropping out. For readability, similar programs such as ‘Economics’ and ‘Economics and Business Economics’ are grouped, and all the different Master programs are grouped as one.

As reported in “Student dropout from universities in Europe: A review of empirical literature”, the *information dimension* is dependent on both the university and the personal preferences of the student. Therefore, this is a very interesting and crucial dimension, considering both the student and the information provided by the organization are important.

A high dropout rate is a very important issue because it has consequences for various parties that are involved in this decision. For instance, individuals that drop out face challenges finding steady and well-paying jobs [45], even if they hold the same profession as an individual that did finish their computer science degree [48, 38]. Dropouts also have higher mortality rates, poorer health, are more likely to engage in criminal activities, are more likely to require assistance, and are less likely to vote [44]. Moreover, there are negative effects for the academic program and the involved faculty too, as it can be demotivating for instructors, reduce enrollment due to these statistics, and result in reduced diversity if there are certain minorities more likely to drop out [34].

There is a worldwide shortage of computer science professionals with the necessary knowledge and skills, and the underlying problem does not appear to be a shortage of people who are interested in this field but rather those who do not finish their degree [33]. If the number of people who drop out early can be reduced, it will have a positive effect on all the consequences mentioned above. This thesis will focus on reducing dropout rates by focusing on information, analyzing the information gap, and looking at how to best represent the information that is available about the program.

1.2 Research question

In this thesis, the aim is to answer the following central question:

- **RQ:** *How can the information visualization be improved to help prospective students choose a study program for the BSc Informatica?*

This question will be divided into the following sub-questions:

- **SQ₁:** *What is the information gap?*

The answer to this question should identify the information gap by getting insight into the current decision process. We can learn about both their positive and negative experiences through their process. In addition, insight into their process gives an idea of what information they use to make their decision and how they acquire it. The combination of these two aspects will indicate the existing information gap and provide the basis for a solution. This will be done specifically for the College of Informatics and might not apply to other colleges and faculties.

- **SQ₂:** *How can information presentation be customized to differentiate similar study programs?*

The second part of the two-part central research question is related to customizable information. The answer to this second subquestion will provide insight into the possibilities concerning customizable information. The techniques found can be used to customize the available information in such a way that it helps students choose a study program.

- **SQ₃:** *How can a new information visualization tool remain maintainable?*

A new information visualization tool should be easily maintained after this graduation project, and it should be easy to understand. This includes the fact that the included information should be able to be adapted according to the needs of the students and the demands of the lecturers.

1.3 Contribution

This thesis presents contributions to the field of reducing dropout rates at the University of Amsterdam for the bachelor programs *Informatica*, *Informatiekunde*, and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie*. First, we aim to identify the information gap that influences the dropout rate. Using this information, we aim to propose a method and a corresponding framework that could be used to help students in their decision-making for the bachelor's program *Informatica*, based on the experiences of College of Informatics students. Furthermore, the project will provide the basis for further research into this subject and the development of new information systems. This tool will not replace any system but exist as an addition.

1.4 Outline of thesis

The second chapter of this thesis will further examine the problem by first exploring how other studies have minimized the dropout rate and then proposing several methods that have been used to provide customized information. Chapter three will provide the methodology and explain the different methods that will be used for the different steps. In the fourth chapter, the problem will be analyzed with both theoretical information and real-world data. In chapter five, the conclusion from chapter four will be used to design a prototype that could be used to help students in their decision-making process. The sixth chapter will collect feedback and examine the effectiveness of my design. In the following seventh chapter, the results will be interpreted, and limitations will be discussed. After this discussion, the following eighth chapter concludes the thesis. The final chapter suggests future research.

Related work

The research question consists of two components: the education part and the information part. The education component of this question involves the students and how they make their choices. Previous studies on this subject should give insight into what solutions have already been explored in the literature to reduce the dropout rate and which reasons for dropping out have been found. The analysis of these studies will contribute to understanding the underlying factors.

The information component is focused on how to display and manage the information. The studies on customizable information should result in an overview of the different possible customization techniques, combined with requirements to determine when a technique is useful. By examining the existing literature, these methods could be used in the creation of the design.

By combining the education and information components, the related work forms the basis of this project.

2.1 Previous studies on dropping out

As explored in the introduction, dropout rates, and information presentation and visualization are currently lively topics.

2.1.1 Predicting dropouts

A significant number of recent studies have focused on predicting dropouts [42], with some of them targeting programming courses, some of them targeting online courses, or study programs in general.

Because this is currently a topic of much research, some studies are not about the actual prediction but about which models make the best predictions. In a study where they look at six different approaches: Logistic regression (LR), Decision Tree (DT), Naïve Bayes classifier (NB), Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Neural Network (NN), they calculate the accuracy, recall, precision, $F1_{score}$ (the balance between two measures of classification), and the classification error rate [30]. The found methods produced accuracy values between 77 and 93 %; the Random Forest classifier had the best scores, and the Logistic Regression model had the fastest execution time.

This Random Forest method is used in a different study on a German dataset [11]. This extensive research predicts early dropouts in three steps. The first step only includes factors that are not related to the study: gender, previous education, and social background. The second step includes information in the decision phase of choosing a study, such as information sources, which is the phase of interest for this thesis. The last step will include the first phases of the study, such as commitment and integration. In all the steps, the grade in the previous education showed itself to be the most important indicator. Based on the results that are found in this research, there is a suggestion that universities should prevent dropping out by helping

students obtain detailed information about the field and setting realistic expectations. This is exactly what will be researched in this thesis.

Furthermore, studies that target programming courses focus on several aspects of programming assignments and require monitoring of the student. In a study involving an *Embedded Systems* programming course at a university in Germany [24], this is combined with a questionnaire to get more background information: to find out how much prior knowledge the student had about any specific subject, motivational beliefs, and (expected) time organization. Both this study and a similar study conducted in Brazil [39] had their focus on several aspects: they focused on the number of lines in a program, correctness, and time; the study in Germany looked into the time it took before students started programming after the assignment was published (time delay), and the study in Brazil looked more into the time the coding took; *keystroke latency*. Related to the correctness, “Drop-out in programming courses – prediction and prevention” also investigated errors: both the total number of errors and error streaks (repeatedly getting the same error message). Both studies have found indicators in monitoring the students: most importantly, the time seems to be a good indicator, as does the error streak. Furthermore, the additional questionnaire showed a strong relationship between the dropouts and a lack of programming experience; this suggested that any preparation courses for specific programming languages could have a significant impact on the performance of their students. Finally, the studies suggest some form of intervention: these analytics could easily identify the students who need additional support on certain topics, which could lead to improved performance. This is a very interesting research direction, due to the presence of programming courses in *Informatika*, *Informatiekunde*, and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* bachelors.

Another approach that is frequently seen is based on student interaction. The studies mentioned above are also related to student interaction, but specifically to the environment where they write their code. A study involving online environments [35] shows the positive correlation between students’ interaction with the system and their measured performance: in the second week, the dropout rate can be predicted with an accuracy of 82% based on this metric.

2.1.2 Drop out motivation

Another approach to addressing this issue involves researching the motivations that lead students to drop out of a study program.

One aspect to consider is the effect of having a job outside of their academic studies. Researchers have interviewed and studied students from a Hungarian university [13], to investigate the effect of employment on the students’ performances. Their findings indicate a strong correlation between employment and dropping out; students who have financial difficulties, a need for work experience, or a desire for independence are more likely to drop out. Another study, conducted at the same Hungarian university [12], examined multiple factors: the sociocultural background, years before higher education, motivation for the choice of higher education institution, employment, sport, and entertainment. In particular, the previous educational career, inappropriate study selection, employment, and competitive sports have a negative effect on performance, potentially leading to dropouts.

As briefly mentioned, this study also addresses the issue of the lack of information as an important factor in the decision-making process [32]. This is strongly related to the subject of this thesis, but there are notable differences, such as the different educational systems in Hungary. A very important part is that some institutions do not require any tuition fee, which is of great influence in the decision-making process.

While this study already addressed the importance of sociocultural background, there has been more extensive research, including data from a wider range of countries. A study including student factors, family characteristics, integration, institution factors, and labor market conditions found effects on the dropout rate in every category [1]. This means that, for example, the category concerning self-awareness concludes that optimism results in being more likely to drop out due to underestimation of the subject. Additionally, the study looked into the services that are offered by the institution, which include the information that is available for students to help them choose a study program. Researchers found that a lack of quantity or quality increased the chance of dropping out.

2.2 Previous studies on customizable information

2.2.1 The risk of customizing information

Customizable information could require personal data. This means that a big part of the usage of customizable information is the "willingness to provide personal information", which is essential to being able to customize anything. Research shows that it is very important that customers, and thus users, know what data will be collected [36]. If they know exactly what it is used for, they are more likely to provide qualitative and more detailed data, which is useful for the system and for the user itself. The better the data that the user provides, the better the results they will receive. Similar to this point, while there keeps coming more and more data, humans do not have more attention or time nowadays [15]; this means that the ability to customize their information should be worth their time.

2.2.2 Methods to customize information

There has been much research done, and there are many patents and frameworks for providing customizable information in several different ways. These methods could be roughly split into two separate groups based on how the user information is gathered. The first group is based on explicit user action; this could mean that the user needs to answer some questions or select some options, and based on this, the customized information will be shown. For the second group, implicit user action, the personalized information will be based on analysis, such as location, but also previous choices [21, 40].

Explicit user action

One of the proposed frameworks is "A Highly Customizable Information Visualization Framework", which exists of three different layers: Data Input, Graph Chooser, and View/Personalization. In the first layer, the data will be received from the database in JSON format, and the metadata will be created. This can be used to determine the *graphic family*, which is a collection of visualizations that serves a particular purpose. The second layer will choose the correct graphic family for this data based on the provided metadata and data. This layer also queries the database because it needs the required graph settings. In the last layer, both the personalization selected by the user and the visualization are handled. Finally, this layer also interacts with the database by storing individual graph settings. The experiments in this work also show the earlier-mentioned time aspect of customizable information. The participants who decided not to make any personalizations while executing their tasks had a significantly lower completion time but also lower accuracy. This seems to be a trade-off for the user; the process either takes less time or is more accurate [47].

A different approach could be that the data is not necessarily different per user, but that the user has *freedom* in using it: they could navigate through the information by themselves while only reviewing the information they are interested in. This would require a form of visualization, such as an interactive graph or chart. It is important to make this an interactive system since not interactive visual representation cannot satisfy all the needs [19]. If the data is structured and there are relations, it will be possible to visualize the data using the characteristics of a graph [25]. Using an information visualization graph also introduces new types of issues, such as making sure it stays understandable and readable, independent of the amount of data. Common issues are the crossing of edges, the size of the graph, and the time complexity. There are many different types of interactive graph visualization systems, such as the Coordinated Graph Visualization [49]; this graph is focused on the interaction aspect of the system. Another example is the Sunburst chart, which has a radial layout and is capable of showing hierarchies in the data [50].

Implicit user action

One way of using implicit user actions would be by analyzing user behavioral patterns, which is done in "Providing Customised Information Panel Content Based on User Behavioral Patterns".

Many applications on the devices of users can collect different types of data, which can be used for analysis. There are various ways to do this analysis, and machine learning is a very popular approach. Even though machine learning is a very useful approach for classifying, it is mainly successful in the case of images, audio, or very large data sets. In the case of time-based data, it is not suitable for classification, and a different method is required [22, 40]. This leads to different approaches, such as using personas. A persona would mean that every persona exists as a set of properties to which a user can be matched, with, for example, a decision tree. There are different types of personas: short-term and long-term profiles. As the terms describe, a short-term profile means temporary behavior, such as a sudden need or interest. A long-term profile will contain information and characteristics that will be valid for a longer amount of time and does not frequently change [21]. In creating such a user profile, there are two different approaches; explicit and implicit. Explicit information collection generally involves some sort of survey, where the user answers questions, on which the persona will be based. For implicit information collection, techniques such as the browser cache or search logs will be used. In [40], the places a user visits are used to present personas for typical users. However, every method will have its pros and cons. One of the general negative points of implicit data collection is that the user *must* use specific software or *must* enable cookies; otherwise, there is no data.

There are several ways to represent a user profile, and “User Profiles for Personalized Information Access” [21] shows three of them: keyword profiles, semantic network profiles, and concept profiles.

Keyword profiles are the most common type of user profile. Every profile exists of multiple keywords: a keyword vector that also exists of weights. This way, whenever a user enters the system, this data can be seen as a weighted keyword vector, which can be matched with any of the profiles [46]. Keyword profiles can be created from both implicit and explicit data collection techniques, and the weights can be calculated using *Term frequency-inverse document frequency* (tf*idf).

Semantic network profiles are weighted networks where every node inside the network is a concept; these nodes are called planets. Every planet is representative, and the more data is collected, the more associated keywords will be connected to the planets: these new types of nodes are called satellites. Planets that frequently occur together will be linked, and satellites that are associated with each other will too. The profiles are frequently built using explicit information. The fact that these profiles can contain higher-level concepts, is both a positive and negative point: it models the natural language better, but an existing mapping between the words is required. In a simple system, every user is one network; as the user uses the system, it will be matched.

Finally, concept profiles are also represented by nodes, but here nodes represent abstract topics, instead of specific words. The easiest way to do this is by assigning numerical values to the topic, to show the interest of the user in this topic. Every technique that is used to construct such a profile needs a way to determine how interested a user is in a topic, and most of the techniques use data that is implicitly collected. Some of the techniques that are used are tree coloring, clustering, and text classification.

Another technique for classifying based on implicit user action is the use of an artificial neural network. The reason that “An Information System for Brownfield Regeneration: providing customised information according to stakeholders’ characteristics and needs” uses this technique is that it has no a priori knowledge; the system should develop based on user input and be able to handle data gaps. This very specific project to personalize information was exactly what they needed to answer the information needs of the stakeholders [43].

2.3 Gap analysis

Research shows that analyzing and preventing dropouts is a current topic of interest, and there have been many proposed systems to predict dropouts. However, there has not been research on preventing these dropouts. More specifically, there has not been any research that evaluates the current information presentation and visualization; there is no research on identifying an information gap.

The research on the customization methods shows there are many different methods, and that they can be roughly split up into two categories: explicit and implicit user action.

The project needs data collection in such a way that real-world data can be analyzed to examine the information gap and find out what the problems are in the information presentation. The found customization methods can be used to create the design

Methodology

3.1 Overview

While there is a significant amount of research in this field, none of it covers the contribution this thesis will make. The project can be split up into three parts: problem analysis, design, and feedback collection. The first step is problem analysis, and the methods will be discussed in detail in 3.2. This step starts with a more theoretical analysis. Subsequently, to find out how students experience choosing a study program and which information they use to make their decision, we mainly use questionnaires to collect the data. This data collection will be discussed in 3.2.2 and 3.2.3. In addition to these results, there will be interviews, which will be discussed in 3.2.4. With this analysis, the information gap can be identified.

The identified gap can be used to determine which information should be customized and how this should be done—which customization method will be used. This methodology will be discussed in 3.3. The prototypes will be created to provide a bridge between the needs of a student and the available content.

The final step is feedback collection, in which the decisions that have been made need to be verified with students. The methodology will be discussed in 3.4. The flow of this entire process can be seen in figure 3.1.

Figure 3.1: The methodology of this graduation project, visualized in a flow chart.

3.2 Problem analysis

To analyze the *information gap*, the first step is to look into decision-making and the importance of information in this process; this will be done using related literature. To further support the problem analysis, this includes an overview of the available information that is provided by the UvA and the sources that are suggested to be used in the decision process.

3.2.1 Overview data collection

For the creation of the questionnaire, there are two important things to keep in mind. We want all the information we need to get insight into the experiences of a student who is choosing a study program, but, to get this information, they need to fill out the survey. This means it is not useful to use very difficult questions or long questionnaires; students are not likely to answer those questions. This is why we tried to use a combination of open questions and closed questions. We created two different questionnaires since we both want insight from current students in the College of Informatics and from high school students that are in the middle of their process. The questions from the questionnaires are included in the appendices (Appendix A and Appendix B).

3.2.2 College of Informatics students questionnaire

Hypothesis

With this questionnaire, we want an indication of what information students were missing in their decision-making process or which specific component they would like to see changed. Based on what the most frequently commented information is, we will need to use the results from the questionnaire to find out what type of students might specifically need this information.

Content

Current students have already made their study choices, but why and how did they choose their current program? We first have a more general section, followed up by a section about the information facilities, their expectations, and space for comments or feedback (Appendix A).

3.2.3 High School students questionnaire

For the high school students, we were able to target students that participated in the *BSc Informatica* matching; this does not guarantee they will follow the program, but they are interested.

Hypothesis

With this questionnaire, we hope to confirm the findings from the questionnaire for the current students. If the data complement each other, it will provide a more profound basis.

Content

In this questionnaire, we do not need as much information as from the current students. We still ask them about the information facilities, but we now also ask them more about their process (Appendix B).

3.2.4 Interviews

The possibility of doing interviews will give a further understanding of students and their decision-making process since the questions can be personalized to the student. Some of the interviews will be particularly based on the data the students provided in the forms, which makes it possible to focus on specific interesting components.

The interviews with prospective students can focus on confirming the plan that is based on the current student's experiences by asking them if they had any difficulties finding the information and confirming other possible findings that were found from the questionnaire.

3.2.5 Ethical Considerations in data collection

Since this research involves a questionnaire that involves data from people, there are a lot of different things to consider. The most important thing to mention is that we do not use any personal data; we simply do not need it for processing and analyzing our data. We can only acquire personal information when the student explicitly mentions that we can get in touch with them; this is confidential information that we won't be sharing with anybody. Although we do not use any private information, there are several important points that we have considered. For instance, none of the participants have been obligated to participate in our research project. We have informed them in the description of the form that this survey is anonymous and does not use any private data. We follow the guidelines of the UvA and have had the approval of the Ethics Committee.

There are also some considerations concerning the actual questions. First of all, we tried to avoid any sensitive questions. Dropping out of a program, or even having difficulties within a program, can be a very personal matter; we avoid any questions involving the performance of the student or their expectations of finishing their program. Similar to the previous point about the content of the question, we wanted to make sure to avoid any bias in any of the questions. Besides the fact that we are the ones that created this questionnaire and project, we are also the target: students of the *BSc Informatica* who also made their study choice a few years ago. However, we do not want to influence their response by not using objective questions. Similarly, asking open questions also prevents unwanted bias by not making any suggestions in specific questions.

3.2.6 Data analysis

Because there are both open and closed questions in the questionnaire, this means that it is both qualitative and quantitative research. For the open questions, the answers need to be coded; different answers might be grouped if they mean the same thing. The biggest part of the analysis is visualizing the data. This is done using Python and several libraries: NumPy, Pandas, and Matplotlib. This analysis should conclude by identifying the gap.

3.3 Design

We will propose a system to bridge the gap identified in the previous step.

3.3.1 Determine missing information

Based on what has been identified as the information gap, it will be necessary to determine which information needs to be shown and how the information needs to be shown. This will fully depend on what the information gap indicates, and it includes exploring if any methods are already available through the study program.

3.3.2 Propose customization method

The information that has been found in the previous step and the data analysis will be combined to determine which customization method can be used. This will be done by comparing the requirements of the customization methods that have been found in 2.2.2 and the found data.

3.3.3 Design and implementation

The combination of the information that needs to be visualized and the customization method will result in the design and how it should be implemented.

Design hypothesis

Students have a lot of different sources to consult in their decision-making process, but they will probably not use all of them. This could be because they cannot find the information, which would be shown through the questionnaire results, or because they are sure enough about their choice and do not think they need the information. Figure 1.3 showed that almost 25 % of the *Informatica* dropouts transfer to one of the other College of Informatics bachelors, which indicates that the difference between the three different programs might not be clear; this can be shown with the results of the questionnaires and the interviews too. The proposed tool should help them.

Based on the questionnaire, it might be possible to create a user profile with the provided information. Based on the different user profiles discussed in 2.2.2, it is most likely that a user profile based on keywords will be created based on the keywords we ask for in the questionnaire. The use of user profiles requires implicit user action, but in this project, it would not be possible to implicitly collect the data. This means that this would require explicit data collection—implicit user action through explicit data collection. If the data does not support the use of a user profile, explicit user action will be required. This would focus on a specific information facility that would be missing or not clear. In both cases, the data will be used for the creation of the prototypes.

3.4 Feedback collection

Measuring the success of the prototype is a very interesting, but difficult part of this project, for various reasons. First of all, it is not possible to redesign the entire UvA system or integrate it with the UvA system within the scope of this project; therefore, it is impossible to compare the experience. Besides this point, students have already made their study choice; the deadline is the first day of May [2, 3, 4].

Except for measuring success, it is important to determine what success means in this context. It is impossible to determine absolute success, which would mean seeing if students who use this new prototype are more likely to successfully finish their degrees. However, since we want to help students make a decision, success would mean that they are more sure about the study choice that they made, which would hopefully result in them finishing their program.

The collection of feedback can be split up into two stages. Verification of the chosen information, and the verification of the chosen customization.

3.4.1 Verification chosen information

Based on the identified gap, a specific information component will be chosen in the design. This step in the feedback collection consists of interviewing students and having them review the information that I chose. This means that we will discuss if they think it would be helpful to share this information with students who are making their study choices.

3.4.2 Verification chosen methods

The way to measure the success of the visualization methods is to let the users experience the prototypes. This would mean we need to question how they experience the tool and what they think about it. The feedback for the different prototypes can be compared and will result in insight into what students prefer and how the information should be presented. This will result in the answer to the research question. Users that use the tool should be asked questions in several categories: their satisfaction with the experience, how accurate they think the visualization is, how engaged they are, and how useful they think this would be. This will be used to determine the overall effectiveness. The questionnaire is included in the appendix (see Appendix C).

Problem analysis

To get insight into how students select a study program, it is important to know more about the decision-making process and the role of information gathering in this process.

4.1 Theoretical Analysis

4.1.1 How do humans make decisions?

There are a lot of different directions possible when looking at this well-studied question. One approach would be to classify every decision as either a riskless choice or a risky choice [17]. For the riskless choice, the biggest assumption is that the person who makes the choice is an *economic man*. This means the person is completely informed (and thus has all the related information, including the consequences of possible action), infinitely sensitive (which means that they would be able to detect the smallest changes), and rational (every choice is made to maximize the outcome, and there are preferences between several options). The theory of risky choices is about both risk and uncertainty and consists of trying to maximize the expected utility, which can be done in a mathematical formula to calculate and maximize the *expected value* (EV). The following formula (equation 4.1) is used to calculate the EV, where p is the probability and $\$$ is the value of an outcome.

$$EV = p_1\$_1 + p_2\$_2 + \dots + p_n\$_n \quad (4.1)$$

However, the expected value as explained in “The theory of decision making.” is often seen as a poor predictor of choice since there are many more factors involved in making a risky decision [41]. This results in the usage of an *expected utility* instead of an expected value, where people are, for example, influenced by the history of the decisions they have made. If the consequences of a decision are unknown, and thus there is uncertainty, this has a big influence on the decision-making process due to specific brain systems. However, to completely understand the risk-sensitive decision-making process, extensive research on all the fields of this topic is required [41].

Selecting a study choice is a decision that is not riskless. It is very difficult to be completely informed; even if all the data is known to a student who is trying to choose a program, it is not possible to know all the consequences of all the possible actions during the study program. On top of that, it is also the case that making the *wrong choice*, which in this case means not successfully finishing the study program, could have various consequences.

Making a decision is essentially a process: a decision-making process, which means it exists in various stages. These different stages could be seen as the required steps to make the decisions and are defined as a list of instructions [20]. Making a decision implies that there are multiple options and, thus, alternatives; this means we need to find the option that is the best fit for the defined goal and objectives.

The steps of the decision-making process are:

1. Stating the issue
2. Set requirements
3. Set goals
4. Recognize different approaches
5. Set criteria
6. Choose a tool to make the decision
7. Check the different approaches
8. Verify solution

There are many available methods and analyses for humans to make their decisions, which are not equally useful for making a study choice because of the characteristics of choosing a study program. There are several different questions that students will have to ask themselves when choosing a bachelor's program: if they want to study at a university, at which university they want to study, and what study program they want to follow. This means that there are several decisions that they will have to make. All these separate decisions have multiple criteria, depending on the student's needs, such as previous achievements and the teacher's characteristics [9], entry requirements [14], and job opportunities [16]. A good outcome would be a study program that helps a student achieve their goals (both during and after the study) and matches the student's abilities with the requirements, and the student is interested in the content of the study [10]. The process of this decision process can be split up into three stages, according to "An innovative stakeholder framework for the Student-Choice Decision making process"[18]: "Need Recognition", "Evaluation of Tertiary Institutions", and "Tertiary Institution Choice & Enrolment".

Stage 1: Need Recognition

This stage is shown to be affected by internal and external factors, such as parents, friends, teachers, society, culture, and ambitions. Besides these factors, the needs of students are also determined by their characteristics, such as age and gender. These characteristics also include their family, for example, their expectations, and their income.

Stage 2: Evaluation of Tertiary Institutions

The next step, and thus the second stage of this process, is related to the characteristics of the institution itself. In theory, at this point, the student knows what they need and want from their education. Factors such as the location of the institution, the characteristics of the college, and its reputation become relevant. Furthermore, characteristics such as the student's abilities, interests, and motivation become more important.

Stage 3: Tertiary Institution Choice & Enrolment

In the final stage, there is some overlap with the previous stage(s). However, at this point, the opinions of parents and where high school friends will enroll or have enrolled also become important. Factors such as how satisfied current students are become important too.

Information gathering

This research has shown that every stage consists of "Innovative Information Gathering & Information Sources", but that the sources per stage differ. In the first stage, students use information from the people that are close to them and online information; websites and social media are a big part of this. In the next stage, university marketing and the people involved with the university, both students and staff, become important as well. In the final stage, the earlier mentioned satisfaction level, people they are close with, and admissions become important.

4.1.2 Available tools

“An innovative stakeholder framework for the Student-Choice Decision making process” has shown the importance of the available information sources and thus, the significance of the presentation of the information. Students that are interested in one of the bachelors of the College of Informatics, can use several sources that are presented by the University of Amsterdam. These tools can be grouped into physical activities and online activities. Due to COVID-19, there has been a shift in these activities; some activities have always been on campus and were forced to be moved to an online environment: some of these have returned to campus and some of them stayed online.

Online activities

The *UvA Studiescanner*, *Bachelor’s Week*, website, and social media are the online tools that are available online and presented by the university itself. The UvA websites will be the starting point for many high school students in choosing a study program. The page of a bachelor’s program will consist of personalized information, but the main page will have some general components: a short and general introduction, five reasons to study the program, some practical information, and several links to different types of information, such as student experiences, the curriculum, and possible jobs after you finish the degree. One of the other links is to a document called “Vergelijking bacheloropleidingen in de informatiewetenschappen” (Comparison of the Bachelor Programs in the College of Informatics). This overview gives a comparison of the three different bachelor’s programs with a short description of some subjects that are specific to the program, admission requirements, and prospects [3, 2, 4].

The Bachelor’s Week is an activity for students that choose their study program and who probably already have some information, for example, from the website. This Bachelor’s Week used to be an on-campus day but is now a week that contains online information sessions for all the different bachelor’s programs the UvA offers. You can get in-depth information, hear about student experiences, and ask questions [5]. Currently, one of the recorded sessions can be viewed on the website.

More recently, the UvA created a *studiescanner*, only available in Dutch. This tool contains twenty questions, where every question has two different options, and the user needs to select which of those options interests them the most. In the end, the student receives the bachelor’s programs that best match their interest with a short description; they can swipe the bachelor to the right side of the screen if they are interested. In the end, the preferred bachelor’s programs can be compared.

Finally, the UvA has several different social media channels that are all focused in different directions. There are accounts for the entire organization, faculties, specific organizations inside the UvA, some of the buildings, and some of the study programs.

Physical Activities

The possible physical activities include *UvA Student for a day*, *Experience Days*, and the *Open Campus Day*.

The *Open Campus Day* that is organized at the different locations in Amsterdam is for students to visit the campus. There will be a guided tour, and it will be possible to explore the building. The activities depend on the program; some will include mini-lectures. Furthermore, there are people present (both students and staff) to answer questions and therefore help in the decision-making process [7].

Both the *UvA Student for a day* and the *Experience Days*, are most likely not the first steps in the decision process. These activities are not necessarily to acquire more theoretical information about a program but to experience the content for yourself. For the UvA Student for a Day, you shadow a current student for a day and join them in their lectures and tutorials [8]. The *Experience Days* are focused on the new students, who will attend a lecture, practical, or tutorial [6], created especially for them.

4.2 Data collection and analysis

4.2.1 Questionnaire results

The results from the questionnaire provide insight into the information gap and show the relationship between several aspects of students' interests and their decision-making process. For this research project, the information aspect is the most interesting part of identifying the information gap. 62 students filled out the survey¹.

Satisfaction and expectations

The average satisfaction of the used information facilities on a scale of one to five is 3.8; this does not differ very much per study program: the average for *BSc Informatica* is 3.9, the average for *BSc Informatiekunde* is 3.7, and for the *BSc Kunstmatige Intelligentie* the average is 3.8. The distribution of the given grades for all three programs can be seen in figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1: The satisfaction of information facilities on a scale from 1 to 5. This includes responses from all three bachelor's programs, and the figure is based on the percentages of all three programs combined.

Similar to this, on a scale of one to five, "Did the study match its expectations?" also received an average of 3.8; here, the *BSc Informatica*, *BSc Informatiekunde* and *BSc Kunstmatige Intelligentie* respectively score an average of 3.9, 3.6, and 3.8. This distribution can be seen in figure 4.2.

¹The data has been cured and stored on the SurfDrive (by the supervisor) for preservation.

Figure 4.2: A score from 1 to 5 on how well the study program matches its expectations. This includes data from all three College of Informatics programs and the percentage is calculated based on all the data combined.

Both scores can be used to determine the quality of the information facilities; the satisfaction of the facilities has a very direct connection with the information gap, and expectations that were not met could be an indication too. If the matching expectations score is very low, this could indicate that the study program itself did not match the information they used to make their study choice. Both scores are sufficient but not very high. There is room for improvement.

Used facilities

Figure 4.3 shows which information facilities are used the most and thus indicates the importance of the information on the UvA website. More than 70% of the students that answered the questionnaire mentioned that they used the UvA website to make their decision. The students that used the UvA website for their decision give an average score of 3.9 when you ask them if the study program matches their expectations; students that did not use the website give an average score of 3.6. There is a difference, but the difference is relatively small; there could be other factors that affected the score.

Figure 4.3: The information facilities that students from *Informatica*, *Informatiekunde*, and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* used to make their study choice, expressed in percentages.

In a separate question on more comments about the use of information facilities, four students explicitly mention the Bachelor’s Week that the UvA organizes as useful. Students that used the Bachelor’s Week give an average score of 3.9 on how the study matches their expectations; students that did not use this activity gave an average score of 3.5.

One of the important aspects of the information gap is the information that is missing. In the questionnaire, students could mention what they missed or what they wish they knew before choosing the program, and the results are shown in figure 4.4.

The common subject "Realistic representation" is divided into several categories (as shown in figure 4.5).

Figure 4.4: This figure shows what students answered when asked what they missed. There are several types of answers in this figure: some of them are very specific, such as *costs*, and some of them are information facilities that exist but were not used. For example, the *Course Catalogue* indicates that students missed specific information on courses or the type of assessments, which can be found in the *Course Catalogue*.

Figure 4.5: This figure shows the exact subjects that students mentioned when they shared that they missed realistic information on a specific subject.

Although there is also a significant part of the students who mention they did not miss any information, figure 4.6 shows that the biggest part of the students did miss information.

Figure 4.6: Did students miss information? This figure shows that the majority of the responding students mentioned that they missed information in their study choice process.

Based on the analyzed data, the next step is to see if there is any direct relation between missing information and other components. Out of the students that had doubts about choosing their bachelor’s program, over 72% missed information in their process: around 25% of them missed information that could have been found in the Course Catalogue, as can be seen in figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: This figure shows a relation between the missing information and the students that had doubts in their decision process.

Besides providing specific missing information, around 18% of the respondents mentioned an information shortage in various questions. 45% of this group of students indicate that they

personally could have done more, while other students simply did not know the information was available.

Realistic representation

The analysis shows that the Course Catalogue and a realistic representation are seen as the information source and information aspect that are missed the most by the students, especially the ones that had doubts about choosing their program. However, putting the focus on improving realistic representation introduces a variety of new issues. First of all, this would require actual new information, which, according to a percentage of the students, is not present on the website. However, the term realistic can be very personal. For example, realistic student experiences, as seen in figure 4.5, could mean different things to different students. For all three College of Informatics programs, there are student experiences available on the websites; whether these experiences are *realistic* for a student differs per student. Acquiring new student experiences to share on the website also introduces more ethical issues. First of all, the experiences provided should not be misleading for marketing reasons. Secondly, the representation could be biased by selecting students that perform well and do not have any issues in their program. This would mean that the students who might be struggling in their education either do not want to share their experiences or that the university could decide not to share their experiences. Finally, it would be simply impossible to share all students' experiences. This would mean that extending the information on students' experiences might go against transparency and accuracy.

Course Catalogue

Contrary to the realistic representation, the Course Catalogue is already there [28]. There is a link to it on the UvA website, but it is not visible, which could explain why so many students did not use it as an information source. Information about the relationship between the bachelor's program and the curriculum seems to be missing for students. Based on the questionnaire, it might be possible to find specific characteristics for students who have missed this information. Figure 4.8 shows that most of the students who missed the Course Catalogue started studying their program due to a specific interest. Looking into the specific interests, the data does not show one specific interest that most of the students were interested in.

Figure 4.8: Reasons why the students who missed the Course Catalogue started studying their program. This could be an indication of a specific user profile.

Prospective students

Based on the answers we found, we can confirm this using the results of the twenty prospective students that filled out the survey. Figure 4.9 shows that the UvA website is also the most used information facility. The Course Catalogue is used relatively more than the current students did (as seen in figure 4.3, but not by a very high percentage. The average satisfaction score is 3.9, and the distribution can be seen in figure 4.10. In comparison with the distribution of the current students (figure 4.1), there is a very high percentage that gives a score of 4 out of 5. Only one student mentioned that they had some trouble finding the explicit schedule on the website.

Figure 4.9: This shows which facilities the students from the Matching used. The scores are expressed in percentages.

Figure 4.10: On a scale of 1 to 5, prospective students rated the information facilities they used.

To confirm the need for the Course Catalogue, we asked students how well they know what to expect from the content of the study program. Here, the assumption is that if students took their time to study the Course Catalogue, they would have a sufficient idea of what to expect from the study program. Figure 4.11 confirms that a lot of students do not know what to expect from the content and the courses in the study program, with an average score of 2.6. Over 50 % of the respondents gave a score lower than 3.

Figure 4.11: Prospective students' scores on how well they know what to expect from the content of the study program.

4.2.2 Interviews

The interviews intended to hear their experiences and confirm the information from the questionnaires.

Current students

Students were asked questions about their decision-making process, the information facilities, and their role in this process. Finally, they were asked specifically about their experiences with the Course Catalogue.

The first interview was with a student in the *BSc Informatica*. She mentioned that she had doubts between *Informatica* and *Informatiekunde*, but the Bachelor's Week helped her in her choice. The *Informatica* information gave her a more clear idea of what she could expect, in contrast with *Informatiekunde*. From her experience, the focus for *Informatiekunde* was on being a multidisciplinary program; this did not give a clear idea of what the actual content of the program itself was, unlike *Informatica*. She used the flyer for her comparison between the programs but shared that this was very *difficult* information, not suitable for students who are not into the jargon of the field. Finally, after bringing up the availability of the Course Catalogue, she mentioned that she thinks that this could have helped her in her decision. This could have made *Informatiekunde* more clear and given a better idea of the bachelor's program she chose. However, she did mention that the Course Catalogue itself might be a little too complicated to use for two main reasons: one is that it is not easy to use and it is difficult to find the information the student is interested in, and the other is that it would be more approachable if the language that is used to describe the content was easier to understand.

The second interview with a *BSc Informatiekunde* student shared a different decision process and mainly used the information from students that he knew who were already in this program. He discussed most of his information with them, and they gave him the clearest idea of what he could expect in the program. He did use the Course Catalogue after his acquaintances told him, and he mentioned that he thought this was a very useful experience to find out the content of the study program. He did not consider the other College of Informatics bachelor programs because he was interested in programming but did not think he had enough programming experience to follow *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* or *Informatica*: he based this on the information he received through conversations with students from both *Informatiekunde* and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie*. After sharing my idea on improving the usage of the Course Catalogue or the information about the content of the program, he acknowledged that not all students are aware of its existence. He also mentioned that in the case of a tool to show the content of a study program, it would be important to not only pick two "interesting" courses but share all of them.

In the third interview, a *BSc Informatica* student shared that he took a lot of time to figure out his student choice, by comparing information from different programs. However, he does not think that all students take as much time browsing for information as he did. He thinks the flyer to compare the three College of Informatics programs is a good starting point, but that it is not clearly visible on the website. In addition to this comparison, he suggests a separate Bachelor's Day for the College of Informatics. This event would then share information on all three programs instead of only one. Besides the comparison of the three programs, he mentioned how useful he thought the content of the Course Catalogue was. However, even despite using this source, he was surprised by the big amount of mathematics courses in the program: this is not explicitly mentioned on the website itself. To make the information about the content even more clear, it would be nice to integrate the content of the Course Catalogue into the website by providing short descriptions of the courses. As a final point, he concludes by saying that *Informatica* is an intense study program, with both studying and doing practical work. There is a big difference between the courses, and he could imagine that not everyone would be able to keep up with that.

Prospective Students

In the interviews with the prospective students, the students were asked questions about their decision process and how they made their decision. This included questions about if they had any difficulties finding information and about how well they knew what to expect from the program and its courses—information that could be found in the Course Catalogue.

Two students did not mention any issues finding the required information to make a decision and did use the Course Catalogue. They did not share any issues with their experience with the Course Catalogue, but they did mention how useful they thought it was. Both students mentioned

that they chose or considered *Informatica* because of specific interests and opportunities. Another student shared a similar experience, but also specifically mentioned the use of the comparison flyer as one of the sources he had used to base his decision on. He shared that he thought this was very useful and gave a clear overview of the differences between the three College of Informatics bachelors. As an answer to why he did not choose the other programs, he mentioned that he did not choose *Informatiekunde*, because he was not interested in statistics courses, such as calculating probabilities. This is a very interesting finding since the Course Catalogue or the website of *Informatiekunde* does not show anything on statistics courses [29]. In comparison, *Informatiekunde* has the fewest statistics courses of all three College of Informatics programs.

A different student shared a very different experience. She mentioned that she was interested in *Informatica* due to related courses in high school and did not consider any other programs besides *Informatica* at other universities. She did not know what to expect from the content of the study program and did not know of the existence of the Course Catalogue. She did mention that she thought it might be useful to look into this.

Another student mentioned that they were interested in psychology but wanted to follow a program that was more focused on the exact sciences. At the information presentation for Artificial Intelligence at the Vrije Universiteit, they realized that this was not *exact* enough and decided to choose *Informatica*. They got most of their information from people who followed similar programs at an education market at their high school. The existence of the Course Catalogue was not known to them, but they also did not need this information. Nevertheless, they said that they did want to know where they could find it so that they could look into it now and have a better idea of what to expect.

A final student shared that he was interested in mathematics and was looking for programs that existed of mathematics courses. With this specific interest, he ended up being interested in the Physics, Mathematics, and *Informatica* bachelor. He did consider the *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* bachelor, but it did not have enough mathematics to become an option. He thought the content of the study program, and thus the Course Catalogue, was the most important source that he used; he not only looked at descriptions of courses but also into the books that were suggested and the lecturers. He would recommend using the Course Catalogue for every student, but he did mention that the design and interface of the Course Catalogue are outdated. He suggested that it would be nice if someone worked on updating this.

4.3 Information gap identification

Based on the above analysis, we can conclude that the Course Catalogue is indicated as the source that students missed the most. The students that I interviewed and used the Course Catalogue explicitly mentioned the usefulness of the Course Catalogue and its content; one of them even mentioned that it would be nice if there would be a better-looking overview of the courses. The responses of the prospective students also confirm this conclusion by indicating that they do not know what to expect from the courses in the program, which is information that could be found in the Course Catalogue.

Contrary to my hypothesis, the data did not show any specific user profile for users that missed the information on the courses; it was more of a general missing component that students could not find or did not use.

Design visualization system

5.1 Chosen information

The prototype will be focused on the content that can be found in the Course Catalogue: this is one of the information facilities that can be improved, as discussed. The Course Catalogue contains information on the content of the study program, such as overall information on the bachelor's program and the courses. Information on the courses is one of the most frequently mentioned specific components that is missing currently. However, students in interviews also mention that it is difficult to use or find for new students because they are not familiar with the system and do not exactly know how it works.

All courses in the Course Catalogue are listed on separate pages, with information in different categories, such as objectives, content, registration, study material, and assessment. This does not show the relation between the courses or to what extent a specific subject or component is part of the program; as seen in the questionnaire results, it would not indicate how much mathematics is in the study program. To show this, we could make use of *Learning Trajectories*. Trajectories are a relatively recently introduced method to split up the courses into different *learning trajectories*. Currently, they are only available to current students; they need to sign in before being able to see them. The *BSc Informatica* can be split into six different *trajectories*:

1. Computer Systems
2. Academic Competences
3. Data and Information Systems
4. Mathematics and Computer Science Theory
5. Modelbased Systems
6. Software Systems

Almost every course from the bachelor's program can be assigned to at least one of these trajectories, according to the *Visible learning trajectories*, which can be found for current students of the program on *Datanose*; an online platform where UvA students can see their schedules and find information about their study program. Table 5.1 shows the different courses placed in the different trajectories.

Trajectories	Courses (in Dutch)
Computer Systems	Architectuur en Computerorganisatie, Besturingssystemen, Distributed and Parallel Programming, Graphics en Game Technologie, Digitale Signaalverwerking, Project Computational Science, Compiler Construction
Academic Competences	Academische Vaardigheden Informatica 1, Architectuur en Computerorganisatie, Internet of Things, Academische Vaardigheden Informatica 2, Distributed and Parallel Programming, Introduction Computational Science, Reflectie op de Digitale Samenleving, Project Software Engineering, Introduction to Security, Moderne Cryptografie, Digitale Signaalverwerking, Virtual and Augmented Reality for Good, Project Computational Science, Klassieke cryptografie, Afstudeerproject Bachelor Informatica
Data and Information Systems	Datastructuren voor IN, Internet of Things, Moderne Databases voor IN/IK, Networks and Network Security, Introduction to Security, Scientific Data Analysis, Digitale Signaalverwerking
Mathematics and Computer Science Theory	Datastructuren voor IN, Discrete Wiskunde en Logica, Lineaire algebra KI/INF, Automaten en Formele Talen, Internet of Things, Algoritmen en Complexiteit, Numerical Recipes Project, Introduction Computational Science, Statistisch Redeneren, Introduction to Computer Vision, Introduction to Security, Moderne Cryptografie, Scientific Data Analysis, Digitale Signaalverwerking, Project Computational Science, Theory of Functional Programming, Klassieke cryptografie
Modelbased Systems	Introduction Computational Science, Introduction to Computer Vision, Graphics en Game Technologie, Scientific Data Analysis, Virtual and Augmented Reality for Good, Project Computational Science
Software Systems	Inleiding Programmeren, Datastructuren voor IN, Programmeertalen, Networks and Network Security, Project Software Engineering, Digitale Signaalverwerking, Theory of Functional Programming

Table 5.1: Trajectories and courses. The courses that are given in Dutch and have a Dutch name have not been translated.

All the mandatory courses are in bold, and only those will be included in the prototypes. This is because, overall, the students are not restricted to the *Informatica* electives. It is also very likely that when students choose their electives, they are already more familiar with the UvA systems and do not need this as much as prospective students. The graduation project is also not included in the tool; to which trajectory this project belongs depends on the content of the project.

5.2 Chosen method

As discussed in section 2.2.2, there are several ways to provide customized information. Figure 4.8 shows there is not one specific user profile that demands the use of the Course Catalogue. This means that the prototype requires explicit user action. To also make this appealing, using interactive graphs is a nice way to visualize data. The use of trajectories means that it should be able to hierarchically show the data in such a way that you can see the different courses in one trajectory together and get an idea of their relationship.

One of the graphs that will be used is the Sunburst chart, which is already discussed in 2.2.2. The other graph is a Treemap: this works the same way as a Sunburst chart but is visually different.

5.3 Design and implementation¹

5.3.1 Sunburst chart

The first prototype is based on a Sunburst chart. In this chart, it is possible to see the different trajectories in the BSc Informatica. The implementation is done in Python, using both Plotly and Dash. Plotly [26] is a library that can be used to create interactive data visualizations. Dash is built on top of Plotly and provides a high-level API. This specific Sunburst chart visualizes the data from the root to the leaves [27].

If the user opens the page, they will see the title, a button, and the actual chart. Clicking on the 'uitleg' button will show a little text on what this tool shows and some quick notes on how to use it. They can immediately get started by reading and clicking on the different trajectories. This is seen in figure 5.1.

Visualisatie van de inhoud van BSc Informatica

uitleg

Deze interactieve tool kan gebruikt worden om een beter inzicht te krijgen in de inhoud van de BSc Informatica. De bachelor is opgedeeld in zes verschillende trajecten: door op een traject te klikken krijg je de vakken te zien. Door op een vak te klikken krijg je enkele kernwoorden te zien die zouden kunnen worden gebruikt om het vak te omschrijven. Voor meer informatie over de inhoud van de bachelor of specifieke vakken, raadpleeg de studiegids.

Figure 5.1: This figure shows what the user sees when they open the tool: All the trajectories from the *BSc Informatica*.

Hovering over the trajectories provides the user with a short list of what you learn in this trajectory. This is based on the information on *Datanose*: it is adapted in such a way that it is active and translated to Dutch (figure 5.2).

¹The source code can be found on https://github.com/mspig/visualization_trajectories

Figure 5.2: The explanation of what the modelbased systems trajectory contains: information on what the student will learn in this trajectory.

The follow-up step will be to click on one of the different trajectories to get more information by seeing the different courses. This not only gives them an idea of the different courses that exist but also shows them the courses that might be related to each other because they are on the same trajectory. This can be seen in figure 5.3. To give more information to the user, hovering over a specific course tells them when in the study program the course is given (assuming the study is followed within the official time period without delays). It also shares that there is more information when the course is clicked, as seen in figure 5.4.

Visualisatie van de inhoud van BSc Informatica

[URley](#)

Figure 5.3: Clicking on the trajectory shows the courses that are inside this trajectory

Figure 5.4: Hovering over a course shows extra information on the course.

If the student clicks on a course, it shows keywords. These keywords are selected based on the content of the Course Catalogue, which shows the content and objectives of this course and can be seen in figure 5.5. There is much more information available per course, and it is not possible to show too much information without it seeming overwhelming. Therefore, students are advised to use the Course Catalogue (as can be seen in figure 5.6).

Figure 5.5: When one of the courses is clicked, it shows a couple of words to describe the course. These words are based on their description in the Course Catalogue.

Figure 5.6: The chart itself does not show much more information. However, students are advised to check out the Course Catalogue when they want more information.

5.3.2 Treemap

The Treemap is designed in a very similar way and almost works the same as the Sunburst chart. The difference is mainly visually: instead of using layers of rings, it uses nested rectangles to show the information. The biggest disadvantage of using the Treemap over the Sunburst is that the Treemap does not support keywords with the same name: clicking on **Beveiling** under **Networks** and **Network Security (DIS)** could bring the user to **Beveiling** under **Networks** and **Network Security (SWS)**. This means that the data needs to be slightly altered in such a way that this does not happen. One easier solution is to add the trajectories to the keywords, resulting in **Beveiling (DIS)** and **Beveiliging (SWS)**. This results in figures 5.7, 5.8, 5.9, 5.10, 5.11, and 5.12.

Visualisatie van de inhoud van BSc Informatica

Uitleg

Deze interactieve tool kan gebruikt worden om een beter inzicht te krijgen in de inhoud van de BSc Informatica. De bachelor is opgedeeld in zes verschillende trajecten: door op een traject te klikken krijg je de vakken te zien. Door op een vak te klikken krijg je enkele kernwoorden te zien die zouden kunnen worden gebruikt om het vak te omschrijven. Voor meer informatie over de inhoud van de bachelor of specifieke vakken, raadpleeg de studiegids.

Figure 5.7: Opening the tool provides a similar view as the Sunburst chart. The different trajectories are shown as different rectangles of different sizes and can be clicked to get more information on the content of the trajectory.

Software Systemen
In dit traject leer je:

- * Programma's ontwikkelen en ontwerpen
- * Het omzetten van een reek instructies in een computeralgoritme en deze vervolgens te implementeren
- * Bepalenderen welk programmeerparadigma het meest geschikt is voor het implementeren van een algoritmes
- * Gegeven software te analyseren, evalueren en aanvullen
- * Geschreven code te structureren en documenteren

Klik om de vakken in dit traject te zien!

Figure 5.8: Hovering over the trajectory also provides the same overview as in the Sunburst chart.

Figure 5.9: After clicking on the trajectory, it shows the different courses inside this trajectory. These courses can be clicked to see more information in the form of keywords.

Figure 5.10: Hovering over the course provides information on when this course is given and how many European Credits it is worth.

Figure 5.11: After clicking on the course, it shows the keywords that can be used to describe the course based on their descriptions in the Course Catalogue. The abbreviation of the trajectory is added to prevent any issues.

Figure 5.12: On top of the Treemap, it shows the path of what the user has clicked so far. This shows the hierarchy while the user is still browsing.

The code structure of the Treemap is almost identical to the structure of the Sunburst chart. This includes the same possibilities to adapt as discussed in 5.3.3.

5.3.3 Possibility to adapt

To make sure that the charts could be adapted to specific wishes, such as teachers that would like different keywords or coordinators that would change the trajectory descriptions, all data is saved in online sheets that are imported into the program files. There are two separate files. The first file, `trajectories,courses,properties,ecs`, contains the specific components for the chart.

	A	B	C	D
1	trajectory	course	property	ecs
2	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Fundamentele concepten(CS)	6
3	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Assembly(CS)	6
4	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Relatie hardware/software(CS)	6
5	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Digitaal rekenen(CS)	6
6	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Binaire representaties(CS)	6
7	Computer Systemen	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie (CS)	Pipeline(CS)	6
8	Computer Systemen	Besturingssystemen (CS)	De rol van het besturingssysteem(CS)	6
9	Computer Systemen	Besturingssystemen (CS)	Scheduling en synchronisatie(CS)	6
10	Computer Systemen	Besturingssystemen (CS)	Geheugenbeheer(CS)	6

Figure 5.13: The file containing the chart's data is structured in such a way that it includes the trajectory, the course, the keyword, and how many European Credits the course is worth. This file is available online.

The other file, `course and trajectory descriptions`, contains the descriptions for the courses and the trajectories; the information that is shown when the user hovers over a specific component in the chart. These descriptions make use of HTML tags, to place new lines and make the text bold.

	A	B
1	Subject	Descriptions
2	Computer Systems	In dit traject leer je: * De belangrijkste onderdelen van een computersysteem opnoem
3	Academische Vaardigheden	In dit traject leer je: * Kritisch denken over het wetenschappelijk proces en de rol van
4	Data en Informatie Systemen	In dit traject leer je: * Verschillende representaties van datastructuren uit te kunnen le
5	Math and Computer Science Theory	In dit traject leer je: * Het begrijpen van wiskundige concepten en stellingen die ten gr
6	Modelgebaseerde systemen	In dit traject leer je: * De toegepaste waarde van model gebaseerde systemen uit te l
7	Software Systemen	In dit traject leer je: * Programma's ontwikkelen en ontwerpen (Creating) * Het ont
8	Academische Vaardigheden Informatica 1	Dit vak wordt gegeven gedurende het eerste jaar. Dit vak is 1 EC waard. Klik
9	Architectuur en Computer Organisatie	Dit vak wordt gegeven in de eerste periode van het eerste jaar. Dit vak is 6 EC waard
10	Inleiding Programmeren	Dit vak wordt gegeven in de eerste periode van het eerste jaar. Dit vak is 6 EC waard

Figure 5.14: The file contains the trajectory or course on one side and the description on the other side.

Using the online CSV files makes it possible to create an *open-tool*, where teachers themselves can provide information, instead of less involved parties.

Feedback collection

As discussed in 3.4, the feedback collection is split up into two verifications. In total, ten participants have tried the system.

6.1 Verification chosen information

Of all of the current students I spoke with, only one of them knew that the trajectories of the *BSc Informatica* existed and used them before. They used this to determine which course belongs in which category, which was required for the application of a master's program. Besides that, none of the current students knew they existed. All the other students shared that the idea of using categories would be very useful and could save time because it can serve as an overarching concept for the entire bachelor's program. One student specifically mentioned that they *tried* to do this themselves before starting the program, with the information that can be found in the Course Catalogue; this took a lot of time because it not only requires visiting all the separate courses, it requires the future student to conclude by themselves in which category a course belongs.

Although it will be useful for browsing, most students agreed on one common negative aspect: how telling and clear are the trajectories? Students shared that they don't think the meaning of the names of the trajectories is very clear; for example, what are *software systems*? Some students have followed the programs for multiple years, but still do not know exactly what the different trajectories mean. This implies that for future students, at least the names of the trajectories might need to be more approachable and self-explainable; otherwise, the use of trajectories might not be more useful at all.

6.2 Verification chosen methods

The different prototypes are questioned in a questionnaire¹, to determine the success. The questions in the questionnaires are in different categories, and all the answers can be compared. The prototypes and the already existing 'Visible learning trajectories' page are questioned to confirm the importance of new visualization methods (figure 6.1). Students that are not yet part of the program, can not access this page themselves.

To improve the experiments, they will be in person. Students can use my device to compare the three visualization methods and use either my device or their own to fill out the survey. To make this a more user-friendly experience, there is a *landing page* from which they can enter all three visualization methods. This page can be seen in 6.2. The QR code links to the questionnaire. The questions from this questionnaire can be seen in Appendix C.

¹The data management complies with the guidelines of the UvA. The raw data can be found on the earlier mentioned GitHub repository

Figure 6.1: The current visualization of the learning trajectories, which can be found on Datanose

Figure 6.2: This is what students see when they start with the experiments on my device. They can click on the three different visualization methods to try them out. They can scan or click the QR code to fill in the survey easily.

As mentioned, the questions are asked in multiple categories. The questions are asked in both positive and negative phrasings. The negatively phrased statements are changed to positive statements for the analysis itself. Therefore, the answers that students provided are *flipped* as well; this means that *totally agrees* changes to *totally disagrees*.

The figures of the results can be found in Appendix D and will be briefly discussed per category, in the following sections.

6.2.1 Satisfaction of the Experience

The following statements are used to determine how satisfied the users are: 'I am overall satisfied', 'It took a long time to find the information', and 'I could have used more instructions and the interface is user friendly'. Figure 6.3 shows the average score of these questions and their standard deviation. The average scores for Datanose, Sunburst, and Treemap are respectively 2.775, 3.8,

and 4; the difference between the Sunburst and the Treemap is relatively small, but the difference with the Datanose visualization is a lot bigger. Besides the lower average level of satisfaction, Datanose also shows a higher standard deviation.

Figure 6.3: The average and the standard deviation for all three visualization methods, in the category Satisfaction of the Experience.

6.2.2 Accuracy

To determine the accuracy, the following statements were used: 'The tool gives a clear image of the content of the study program' and 'I doubted the accuracy of the information'. The average score on the accuracy of Datanose is 3.1, the average score of the Sunburst is 4.15, and the average score of the Treemap is 4.05. Similar to the Satisfaction of the Experience, the Datanose score is lower than the Sunburst and Treemap score, even though the difference is slightly smaller. The standard deviation is similar as well; this can be seen in figure 6.4.

Figure 6.4: The average and the standard deviation for all three visualization methods, in the category Accuracy.

6.2.3 Engagement

For the engagement, 'The tool offers enough variety and options', 'I liked exploring the tool', 'I expected more interactions', and 'I couldn't keep my attention', were used. In this category, the difference between the Sunburst and the Treemap is slightly larger, while the difference between the new visualizations and Datanose is very similar. The Sunburst has the highest score and lowest standard deviation, which are respectively 4.325 and 0.85. The Treemap has an average

score of 3.975 and Datanose has an average score of 2.925; these scores and their standard deviations can be seen in figure 6.5.

Figure 6.5: The average and the standard deviation for all three visualization methods, in the category Engagement.

6.2.4 Usefulness

In the final category, statements 'The tool did not have enough relevant information', 'I think this could have given a clear overview of the program before I started studying', and 'This tool can help future students in their decision' were used. The scores for the visualization methods are less far apart: Datanose, Sunburst, and Treemap have scores of respectively 3.1, 3.7, and 3.87. Figure 6.6 shows the scores and their standard deviations.

Figure 6.6: The average and the standard deviation for all three visualization methods, in the category Engagement.

6.2.5 General notes of participants

Participants also could leave notes and share their thoughts outside the provided statements, for every visualization method.

Datanose

The tool has been described as *ugly* and not easily navigable. The information seems to be incomplete, and it would have been nice if there was a clear description of the trajectories and

a short description of the course. It has been described as a system where it is difficult to find *specific* information, and where you should start in exploring the tool.

Sunburst

This visualization has been described as good-looking and more intuitive. It would be better to make it more readable, by increasing the fonts and sizes, and it would be nice to use more colors or even include images to better explain the keywords. For the structure, it has been mentioned that it would be nice to show more *rings*, in such a way that it makes browsing more easy. To make browsing even easier, one person mentioned that it would be nice to better explain how the chart should be used. Finally, for the structure, it has been mentioned that it would be easier if there could be a distinction between the different years in the program.

Treemap

The Treemap is described as similar to Sunburst, which it is, but less clear and good-looking than the Sunburst chart. Similar to the Sunburst chart, the interface should become more readable by increasing the font size. This chart could have used more text since it contains *almost empty* squares. For the structure, a student mentioned that it could be used to share which courses are in which year; they also implied that combining the Treemap and the Sunburst chart might be nice. Finally, similar to the other two visualization methods, it would be useful to further explain the trajectories and their meaning.

Discussion

7.1 Key findings

7.1.1 The content gap

The problem analysis has shown that in general, students are not dissatisfied with the information facilities that are currently available, with an average satisfaction score of 3.8 on a scale of one to five. However, these scores are not perfect, and students do explicitly mention that they have missed information in their decision-making process. The two most frequently mentioned components were that they missed a realistic representation of a specific portion of the program and that they missed information that could have been found in the Course Catalogue. The students that, for example, wished they knew what courses are given in the first year, how many mathematics courses there are, and what types of assessments there are, could have found this information in the Course Catalogue. It would be very difficult to improve the realistic representation, as discussed in 4.2.1, and thus the Course Catalogue has the best possibilities for improvement.

There has not been a specific user profile found for the need for the Course Catalogue, except that specifically students that doubted their choice wish they could have used this information. This meant that the product, in the end, requires explicit user actions. The information should be customizable using an interactive graph, which demands the need for *categories*: the learning trajectories.

7.1.2 The use of trajectories

The feedback collection shows that *the idea* of using categories is well-received and appreciated, under several conditions and requirements. First of all, it seems like there needs to be a revision of the current trajectories; as they are now, they might not be directly usable for future students.

These findings seem to be confirmed in the verification of the chosen visualization methods, in two different ways. First, the scores for the visualization methods in the category *usefulness* are the closest together, compared to the other categories. Although this particular verification category focuses on the different visualization methods to determine how useful the visualizations are, this category also reflects how useful the trajectories themselves are. The fact that all three methods score relatively high indicates that the trajectories would be useful, regardless of how they would be visualized. Second, the general notes of participants confirm that the information itself should be more clear. This information is directly based on the trajectories and thus indicates that there should be a revision in how the trajectories are described.

7.1.3 Sunburst and Treemap chart

In every category that is used in the feedback collection for the visualizations, the Sunburst and Treemap charts score higher than the current visualization that can be found on Datanose.

There is, however, not a big difference in the scores of the Sunburst and the Treemap. This is not unexpected, since the two visualizations are very similar; they are both interactive graphs, contain the same data, and the interactions are almost the same. On average, the Sunburst visualization has a slightly higher score with a total score of 3.99, while the Treemap has a score of 3.97. This is a very minimal difference and does not indicate that one of the two is *the best*. Instead, this shows that students rate the methods with similar scores, but slightly prefer the Sunburst over the Treemap. They do strongly prefer interactive graphs over the current Datanose visualization.

7.2 Limitations

There are potential limitations to this graduation project. Besides the general time limitation, they could be placed in two categories; the questionnaires and the feedback collection.

7.2.1 The problem analysis questionnaires

The questionnaires that we sent out to current students of the *Informatica*, *Informatiekunde* and *Kunstmatige Intelligentie* bachelor's programs could contain several limitations, mainly because there was almost no data available before this study; almost all data is new. To prevent any bias in the answers, we used open questions. However, labeling the answers could have led to possible mistakes. We could have misinterpreted answers (providing the wrong label) and we could have created labels that were too broad (answers *wrongfully* grouped as one).

Furthermore, the given answers also seem to be influenced by *active* courses: students explicitly mentioned not being interested in specific subjects that could be found in current courses. This implies that if this questionnaire was sent out in a different period, it would have resulted in different answers. For this particular research project, it would probably not have much impact on the results, because it would not directly affect their opinions on the information facilities. However, it would be possible that a clearer user profile would emerge, which would have resulted in a different customization method.

Finally, there is no way to validate the students' answers. We can't confirm if the collected data is *realistic* because we do not have any other data to compare this to. This means that we would not be able to notice if students filled out the survey multiple times or if they did not take it seriously.

7.2.2 Feedback collection

For the feedback collection, there are ten participants in total. For a more complete verification, it would be desirable to have a larger group of people available to validate the program. This was not possible due to the time limitations. Having a larger group would also result in better student distribution. A better student distribution would consist of students from different years, different backgrounds, and different needs, in such a way that it better reflects the current students.

Besides the possible limitations with the current group of participants, doing the experiments in-person could have caused a bias. The students need to evaluate *my* system, while *I* am right next to them. This could cause them to *not* be honest about their answers. However, I do not think this is the case in the results. I shared with all respondents that they had to be *brutally honest*. Moreover, the data does not directly indicate any strong bias among students; none of them have filled in only maximum or minimum scores for specific tools. Therefore, it seems that all participants filled it out deliberately, but there is no way to know for sure.

Furthermore, all experiments have been done using the feedback from current students. However, due to the possibility to adapt (as discussed in section 5.3.3), teachers will also be involved in the maintainability of the tool. Therefore, it would have been useful to collect feedback on how they experienced the tool. They could also validate the chosen keywords.

7.3 Improvements

A follow-up to this study will have to take into account the aforementioned limitations. First, in the process of the questionnaires, we could have changed a part of the open questions to closed questions, which would have changed the research from qualitative to quantitative. The process of creating the questionnaire would require exploring possible interests and possible answers, in such a way that closed questions would still contain all the different possibilities. This way, both bias and mislabeling could be prevented, but the creation of the questionnaire would require more work and time.

The design itself does not show any specific limitations, except for what could have been possible with more time. For example, it might have been nice to further explore specific keywords, in such a way that clicking on them provides the student with even more information. This would require more time and possible consultation with a teacher, for the specific course, but could have been useful; this could help in providing the additional information students requested in the feedback collection.

Finally, the reliability of the results of this project would improve with more participants, both students and teachers. A larger sample group simply gives a better reflection of how effective the tool is.

Conclusion

This research aimed to contribute to the field of dropouts, by identifying the information gap and improving the information visualization. The research question, "*How can the information visualization be improved to help prospective students choose a study program for the BSc Informatica?*", can now be answered using the answers to the subquestions and the results. Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the information visualization can be **improved** by visualizing **the content of the program**, using **trajectories** and an **interactive graph** to visualize them. This is supported by the answers to the subquestions and the collected feedback.

The first subquestion, "*What is the information gap?*", required the analysis of the information gap. We are confident to say that the information gap mainly consists of students not knowing what to expect from the content of their chosen study program. They do not know which courses there are or what the important subjects within the program are, which results in them not knowing what to expect from their bachelor's program. This *missing content* could have been found in the Course Catalogue and has formed the basis for the answer to the research question. The answer to this subquestion highlighted which data should be visualized in the system.

The second subquestion, "*How can information presentation be customized to differentiate similar study programs?*", required finding a method to customize the information presentation. Literature studies have shown that there are two main categories, implicit and explicit user action, in which these methods can be placed. In the case of implicit user actions, data could be implicitly or explicitly collected, with methods such as user profiles. User profiles require there to be data that *fits* in a profile. Explicit user action results in the use of an interactive graph, in which users can browse through the content that is offered. The different possible methods, combined with the results from the first subquestion, resulted in using an interactive graph. This is because the data related to the information gap did not fit in a user profile. An interactive graph that highlights the content of a program can help differentiate the program because it will help students figure out what to expect.

Based on the answers to the first two subquestions, the system could be designed. Subquestion 3, "*How can a new information visualization tool remain maintainable?*", resulted in a specific component of the design and implementation, to make sure that the data management of the tool remains maintainable. This is done by creating well-documented and well-structured code and storing all the data online. The online stored data is structured in a sheet, in such a way that it could be easily adapted and maintained by the parties that are involved in this tool. This could be teachers who want to update the information that can be found in the tool.

The combination of the answers to the subquestions led to the final design, in which the Sunburst and Treemap have been implemented; two different interactive graphs to highlight the learning trajectories. The collected feedback confirms both the use of the trajectories and the chosen visualization methods because both have been well received. However, the results do also show that the trajectories and their descriptions do require some extra attention and revision, to make sure they are useful for future students.

Further research

This research can be seen as the first step of research on reducing the dropout rate and increasing the graduation rate, for the *BSc Informatica*, with a focus on the information facilities. This research could be continued in several ways. Besides executing the earlier-mentioned improvements or continuing to improve the provided system, I will explore two of my recommendations for possible future work.

As concluded, current students do not think the trajectories are clear, and they do not always know what they mean. A group that is involved with the bachelor's program *Informatica* should research what would be the most effective way to make the trajectories more approachable to students. This could lead to alternative titles, clear descriptions, et cetera.

As a second direction for future work, this project does not offer final products but rather provides visualization methods, which are shown in the shape of the implemented *prototypes*. Further research could use the feedback on the two well-received visualization techniques, contrary to Datanose. A new framework, that is less reliant on an existing library, should be designed and implemented. This framework should provide an even better user experience, with for example improving the readability, and could increase the customization possibilities. It would be beneficial to further examine the accessibility, in such a way that every user could enjoy the experience.

In addition to the more general improvements, entirely new additional components could be added. Based on specific interests that a user might have, it could highlight specific parts of the visualization, such as keywords and courses. Students can use this to see if the content of a study program matches their personal interests. The data that is collected in this study already contains keywords that students shared as their interests, which could be used to create such a system and further explore this topic.

Questionnaire Col students

A.1 *Algemene vragen*

- Welke opleiding doe je?
- In welk jaar ben je met die opleiding begonnen?
- Wat is het hoogste opleidingsniveau dat je behaald hebt voordat je je huidige opleiding startte?
- Ben je vóór je huidige opleiding ingeschreven geweest bij een andere opleiding?
- Zo ja, waarom ben je van opleiding gewisseld? (laat dit veld leeg als je op de vorige vraag "nee" geantwoord hebt)
- De volgende vraag hoef je alleen in te vullen als je huidige opleiding BSc Informatica, BSc Informatiekunde of BSc Kunstmatige Intelligentie is. Waarom heb je niet voor een van de andere twee bovengenoemde opleidingen gekozen?
- Heb je getwijfeld tussen verschillende bacheloropleidingen?
- Zo ja, tussen welke opleidingen twijfelde je, en waarom heb je je uiteindelijke keuze gemaakt?
- Als je jouw opleiding in kernwoorden zou moeten omschrijven, welke zou je dan gebruiken? Geef ze door komma's gescheiden ("kernwoord 1, kernwoord 2, ...")
- Als je jouw interesses in kernwoorden zou moeten omschrijven, welke zou je dan gebruiken? Geef ze in hetzelfde format als de vraag hiervoor.

A.2 *Informatievoorzieningen*

- Welke informatievoorziening(en) heb je gebruikt bij het kiezen van je opleiding?
- Hoe tevreden ben je over de informatievoorzieningen die je gebruikt hebt?
- Toelichting vorig antwoord
- Welke informatie miste je bij het maken van je keuze?

A.3 *Verwachtingen*

- Waarom heb je je huidige opleiding gekozen?
- Deze vraag moet je alleen invullen als je een van de bacheloropleidingen voor informatiewetenschappen volgt of gevolgd hebt. Voldoet of voldeed deze opleiding aan de verwachtingen die je er van tevoren van had?
- Toelichting vorig antwoord
- Wat is voor jou het belangrijkste onderwerp binnen je opleiding?
- Wat is voor jou het minst belangrijke onderwerp binnen je opleiding?

A.4 *Ruimte voor opmerkingen en feedback*

- Ruimte voor verdere opmerkingen
- Mogen we contact met je opnemen voor verdere vragen? Zo ja, hoe kunnen we je bereiken?

Questionnaire prospective students

- Welke van deze opleidingen heb je overwogen naast Informatica?
- In hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen op jou van toepassing?
 - Ik vond het moeilijk om een opleiding te kiezen.
 - Ik heb mijn keuze vooral op gevoel of intuïtie gemaakt.
 - Het type baan dat je kan krijgen met een studie heeft niet meegewogen in mijn keuze.
 - Ik heb me ingeschreven bij de eerste opleiding die me leuk leek
 - Voor mijn studiekeuze is het belangrijk dat een vakgebied iets bijdraagt aan de maatschappij.
 - Wat mijn ouders/verzorgers van de opleidingen vonden woog mee in mijn studiekeuze.
 - Wat mijn vrienden vonden was onbelangrijk in mijn studiekeuze.
 - Ik heb mijn studiekeuze deels gebaseerd op cijfers die ik voor verwante vakken haalde op school.
 - Het idee dat ik met een studie later veel geld kan verdienen is niet belangrijk voor mijn keuze.
 - Ik weet precies welke vakken ik in mijn studie ga krijgen, en wat die vakken inhouden.
 - Ik had een systematische aanpak bij het kiezen van een studie.
- Waar heb je de informatie die je nodig had voor je studiekeuze vandaan gehaald?
- Hoe tevreden ben je over de beschikbaarheid van de informatie die je nodig had voor je studiekeuze?
- Toelichting vorige vraag
- Hebben wij je al geïnterviewd tijdens de matching?
- Wil je verder nog iets kwijt over je studiekeuze bij de UvA?

Questionnaire feedback collection

- In hoeverre zijn de volgende stellingen, die gaan over de tool, op jou van toepassing?
 - De tool kan toekomstige studenten helpen om een beslissing te maken
 - Het duurde lang voordat ik de gewenste informatie vond in de tool
 - De interface van de tool is gebruiksvriendelijk
 - Ik had meer ondersteuning of instructies nodig om de tool optimaal te kunnen gebruiken
 - Ik kon mijn aandacht niet bij de tool houden
 - De tool biedt genoeg variaties en opties
 - Ik denk dat dit mij een duidelijk beeld had gegeven van de inhoud van de studie, voordat ik aan mijn studie begon
 - De tool geeft een duidelijk beeld van de inhoud van de studie
 - De tool had niet genoeg relevante informatie
 - Over het algemeen ben ik tevreden met de functionaliteit van de tool
 - Ik vond het leuk om de tool te verkennen
 - Ik had meer interactie verwacht
 - Ik twijfelde aan de nauwkeurigheid van de informatie

Results

D.1 Satisfaction of the experience

Figure D.1: This figure shows the scores for the questions on the satisfaction of the experience, for all three different visualizations.

D.2 Accuracy

Figure D.2: This figure shows the scores for the questions on the accuracy, for all three different visualizations.

D.3 Engagement

Figure D.3: This figure shows the scores for the questions on the engagement, for all three different visualizations.

D.4 Usefulness

Figure D.4: This figure shows the scores for the questions on the usefulness, for all three different visualizations.

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